

Plant Disease Detection and Classification Using Camera and Convolutional Neural Network

(Pegesanan Dan Pengelasan Penyakit Tanaman Menggunakan Kamera Dan Jaringan Saraf Konvolusional)

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ABSTRACT

Based on the data from the Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO), around 1.3 billion tonnes of plants are infected by plant disease. In the past, farmers use eye observation to detect and classify plant disease. However, due to the advanced technology nowadays, plant disease can be easily detected and classified by using image processing. Many researchers are concerned about deep learning technology which is used in image processing to detect and classify plant disease. Plant disease classification is difficult due to the large differences in size, shape, colour, layout, lighting and imaging illumination of plant diseases. CNN is a deep learning neural network designed for processing structured arrays of data such as images. Due to the strong feature extraction capability of convolutional neural networks (CNN), CNN is widely used in computer vision and image recognition among various network architectures used in deep learning. A convolutional neural network contains many convolutional layers stacked on top of each other, each one is capable to recognize more features. In this work, the CNN is able to recognize plant disease accurately with five convolutional layers. The main objective of this study is to develop a deployable model for plant disease classification using web application and desktop application with camera to form a real-time inference vision system. In this work, a CNN model was trained with a public dataset that consists of 19384 potato, pepper and tomato images collected under controlled condition. The selection of the images were due to the facts that they are the most common plants in Malaysia. Different parameters such as epochs, batch size, dropout are used to evaluate the performance of the model. A classification report and confusion matrix were used to evaluate its sensitivity and specificity. The developed desktop and web application was able to recognize three different plant diseases and 15 different categorical disease classes as well as healthy plant leaves. Based on the classification report, the trained model can achieve an accuracy of 97.2% and average F1-score of 97%. In conclusion, the trained CNN model can detect and classify plant disease accurately and can produce a useful information for farmers to apply pesticide more effectively to cure plant disease and benefit the agricultural sector.

Keywords: CNN, Plant Disease Classification, Image processing, Computer Vision, Web Application, Desktop Application, Deep Learning

ABSTRAK

Berdasarkan data dari Organisasi Makanan dan Pertanian (FAO), sekitar 1.3 bilion tan tanaman dijangkiti penyakit tanaman. Pada masa yang lalu, petani menggunakan pemerhatian mata untuk mengesan dan mengelaskan penyakit tanaman. Namun begitu, disebabkan teknologi yang canggih sekarang ini, penyakit tanaman dapat diklasifikasi dengan mudah melalui pemprosesan imej. Ramai penyelidik prihatin terhadap teknologi pembelajaran mendalam yang digunakan dalam pemprosesan imej untuk mengklasifikasi penyakit tanaman. Pengklasifikasi penyakit tanaman sukar dilakukan disebabkan perbezaan besar dalam ukuran, bentuk, warna, susun atur, pencahayaan dan pencahayaan pencitraan penyakit tanaman. CNN adalah rangkaian neural pembelajaran mendalam yang direka untuk memproses susunan data tersusun seperti gambar. Disebabkan oleh kemampuan rangkaian neural konvolusi (CNN), CNN banyak digunakan dalam visi komputer dan klasifikasi imej dalam di antara pelbagai seni bina rangkaian yang digunakan dalam pembelajaran mendalam. Jaringan neural konvolusi mengandungi banyak lapisan konvolusi yang saling bertumpuk, masing-masing mampu mengenali lebih banyak ciri. Dalam kajian ini, CNN dapat mengklasifikasi penyakit tanaman dengan tepat dengan adanya lima lapisan konvolusional. Objektif utama kajian ini adalah untuk membangunkan model yang boleh digunakan

di aplikasi web dan aplikasi desktop dengan kamera untuk mengklasifikasi penyakit tanaman supaya dapat membentuk sistem visi inferensi waktu nyata. Dalam kajian ini, model CNN dilatih dengan set data umum yang terdiri daripada 19384 gambar-gambar kentang, lada dan tomato dalam keadaan terkawal. Pemilihan gambar-gambar adalah disebabkan mereka adalah tanaman-tanaman yang paling biasa di Malaysia. Parameter yang berbeza seperti repetisi, saiz kumpulan. Keciciran adalah digunakan untuk menilai prestasi model. Laporan klasifikasi dan matriks kekeliruan digunakan untuk menilai kepekaan dan kekhususannya. Aplikasi desktop dan web yang dibangunkan dapat mengklasifikasi tiga jenis penyakit tanaman yang berbeza dan 15 kelas penyakit kategori yang berbeza serta daun tumbuh-tumbuhan yang sihat. Berdasarkan laporan klasifikasi, model yang terlatih dapat mencapai ketepatan 97.2% dan purata skor F1 97%. Kesimpulannya, model CNN yang terlatih dapat mengklasifikasi penyakit tanaman dengan tepat dan dapat menghasilkan maklumat yang berguna bagi petani untuk menggunakan racun perosak dengan lebih berkesan untuk menyembuhkan penyakit tanaman dan memanfaatkan sektor pertanian.

Kata Kunci: CNN, Pengesanan Penyakit Tanaman, Pemprosesan Imej, Visi Komputer, Aplikasi Web, Aplikasi Desktop, Pembelajaran Mendalam

INTRODUCTION

According to a report by UC Agriculture and Natural Resource Scientist, loss of crops increased from 10 percent to 40 percent due to plant disease. In developing countries, smallholder farmers generate more than 80% of the agricultural production. Therefore, the loss of crops have terrible consequences to them. Due to the sudden climate change, farmers lose almost all of the crops due to pests and plant diseases mostly caused by harmful viruses and bacteria. Plant diseases can damage crops, thus reducing the availability and access to food, increasing the cost of food. Advances in Computer Vision shows an opportunity to increase the usage of artificial intelligence in computer vision applications in agriculture sector (Bhise 2020). Early detection of plant disease can cure the plant disease more efficiently, thus increasing the crop production. Plant disease classification is difficult due to the unwell defined boundaries of the symptoms on the leaf. The analysis of plant disease images might be difficult due to the bad quality images which are affected by lighting, resolution, weather and more. Furthermore, different plant diseases might have similar symptoms. Therefore, it is very important to develop a model that can overcome some of the challenges and is able to detect and classify the plant diseases accurately.

CNN is specifically applied for Computer Vision applications that involves image detection and classification among various network architectures used in deep learning. The challenges for CNN to detect and classify plant disease is to create a deep network such that nodes, structure of the network and edge weights map the input (the image of a diseased plant) to the output (crop-disease pair) correctly. Object classification is mainly used by deep convolutional neural networks (DCNN) and their variations. DCNN has 5 types, which includes R-CNN, fast R-CNN, GoogleNet, VGGNet and Resnet. DCNN is built upon stacked convolutional neural networks (CNNs) which is a variant of feed-forward network (FFN).

Many research papers have been reviewed based on the general flow of the plant disease classification systems (Santhosh 2019) which consists of image acquisition, image pre-processing, image segmentation, feature extraction and image classification. The plant diseases are classified by extracting the features of plant images (Gajanan 2018) and classifying these features (Dhingra 2017).

According to Yang (2020), many efforts focused on deep learning, in which it is known as DCNN. However, the author stated that the CNN is good enough for image processing and is able to extract enough information. Author has proposed that the combination of shallow CNN and classic machine learning classification algorithm to detect and classify plant disease performs better with fewer parameters than other deep models in terms of precision, recall and F1-score. Srivastava (2021) has also conducted a research to detect and classify plant disease with CNN and has accuracy of 88%. Toda (2019) used CNN by applying a variety of neuron-wise and layer-wise visualization methods to detect and classify plant disease. Number of parameters decreased by 75% due to the removal of many layers that are not necessary. Sladojevic (2016) used deep CNN approach to detect and classify plant disease by using classification method and achieved an average accuracy of 96.3%.

According to Gogul (2017), the main difference between ANN and CNN is that only the last layer of a CNN is fully connected, but each neuron is connected to every other neurons in ANN. The neurons in a CNN layer are not connected to all other neurons, but only connected to a small region of neurons in the previous layer, as compared to ANN. CNN is most useful in image classification due to the unique technique of extracting from lower level features to higher level features in an image. The size of the images will cause ANN to over-fit easily. Larger images will need more powerful processor to process due to complex vector. To compare the performance of three different machine learning method, CNN, ANN and SVM have accuracy of 99%, 94% and 91% respectively during

image classification of vegetation species (Mehmood ul Hasan 2019).

An insufficient number of sample leaf images will lead to overfitting. Therefore, Arsenovic (2019) has conducted a study to use traditional augmentation methods and GAN to increase the dataset size. The trained model has 93.67% accuracy. Future work should be focused on detect and classifying different phase of plant disease in different locations. Author has also applied augmented process which includes transformation, rotations and more to increase dataset. The CNN model trained by Harte (2020) uses augmentation and transfer learning. The trained CNN model has an accuracy of 97.2% and F1 score of more than 96.5% and it is deployed as web application. Rishiikeshwer (2019) has trained a CNN model of 98% accuracy with 3600 augmented datasets but 95% accuracy with 400 leaf images.

Many deep learning models perform badly once the model is tested on independent data. Therefore, various studies on how segmented images can improve accuracy of the model are conducted. Chowdhury (2021) and Paul Sharma (2020) conducted the study to solve the problem by using segmented image data to train the CNN models. Sharma (2020) demonstrated that the S-CNN model trained using segmented images has accuracy of 98.6% when tested on independent data as compared to the F-CNN model that is trained using full images. Chowdhury (2021) shows accuracy, IoU and Dice score of 98.66%, 98.5%, and 98.73% for the modified U-net segmentation model. The six-class classification and binary classification of EfficientNet-B7 has achieved an accuracy of 99.12% and 99.95% respectively. Finally, EfficientNet-B4 that uses segmented images for ten-class classification achieved an accuracy of 99.89%. This work can improve the applicability of real-time monitoring in classification of plant disease. However, the limitation in this research is that the model is very sensitive to the quality of segmentation of images. Hassan (2021) has used InceptionV3, MobileNetV2, InceptionResnetV2 and EfficientNetB0 to detect and classify plant disease. By splitting the dataset into 80-20, which is 80% train images and 20% test images, the computation cost and number of parameters have reduced. EfficientNetB0 model has 99.6% accuracy. 565 and 545 s/ epoch were needed to train the images in the MobileNetV2 and EfficientNetB0 architectures respectively on coloured images. Thus, MobileNetV2 can be easily run on mobile devices due to the parameter number and operations that have been limited.

In CNN, the flow of information has no feedback from the output layer to the previous layers. Normal CNN has two or three layers but DCNN has more than 5 hidden layers. Therefore, DCNN can extract more features and its

implementation is better in terms of higher accuracy. CNN has input, hidden, and output layers. The hidden layers in CNN consist of pooling layers, convolutional layers and fully connected layers.

Convolutional layers in CNN are sets of image filters convoluted to pooling layer and feature maps or images. Feature maps are extracted through convolution and other processing layers repetitively in image classification (P.M. Jacob 2020). A label is then outputted by the network which indicates an estimated class. Features in train dataset that can solve the classification problem is generated by the optimization of weights and filter parameters by CNN in the hidden layer so that the time taken to achieve best learning in CNN can be lowered. Gradient descent and back-propagation approaches can optimize the parameters in the network by updating the weights in each image in the training set repetitively to minimize the classification error (Sagar 2020). Different models of neural networks may overfit differently, thus dropout layer is needed to reduce overfitting.

Various papers also presented mobile phone application and web application to detect and classify plant disease by using the trained model. Petrellis (2017) has developed a mobile phone application to monitor plant disease and has achieved accuracy of more than 90%. Rishiikeshwer (2019) has trained a CNN model to be deployed on IoT Web Application that is developed to capture, process and show the predicted plant disease name. A CNN model that has been trained by Ramcharan (2019) is deployed in a mobile app. F1-score is used to evaluate its performance on mobile images. Recall of the model decreases. Therefore, the performance of F1-score decreased by 32% for real world images and video. It is very important to provide enough images to train the CNN model so that the model can be used in real world applications.

There is a limited study to deploy the CNN model with real world applications for plant disease classification. Therefore, this work aims to develop a real-time inference vision system that can detect and classify plant disease accurately with web application, desktop application and Pixy2 camera. The plant diseases can be identified at early stage by using various image processing techniques. The CNN plant disease classification model was trained using OpenCV, python and 20638 healthy and diseased potato, pepper and tomato images. The model was able to detect and classify plant disease through the various coloured spots and patterns on the leaf of the affected plant. The integration of developed model with a camera formed a real-time inference vision system to help the amateurs and trained professionals to verify the diagnosis of plant disease.

METHODOLOGY

The Sequential model was used in this work. An application-based software integrated with Pixy2 camera to form a real-time inference of vision system is proposed. Various libraries like Tensor flow, numpy, matplotlib, os, sklearn, pandas, cv2, seaborn and more were imported. The Sequential model is built in python by using Tensor flow version 2.3.0 and Keras frameworks. The Sequential model behaves like a Functional API model, in which every layer has an input and output attribute to extract the outputs of all intermediate layers in a Sequential model. A CNN model is trained to detect and classify plant disease. Figure 1 shows the plant disease classification system overview using deep learning. The real inference vision system consists of two main parts, in which it consists of training and testing of the model and the real time inference vision system. The real time inference vision system consists of two main parts which is Pixy2 camera and web and desktop applications with CNN model to detect and classify plant disease.

FIGURE 1. System overview

Dataset and model architecture

A publicly available dataset which consist of 20638 images of healthy and diseased potato, pepper and tomato images collected under controlled condition was downloaded from Kaggle. The training and test directories were created from the dataset. Since the model has been decided to be sequential model, validation set was not needed. The train dataset has 19384 images, and the test dataset has 1254 images belonging to 15 different categorical classes. The number of images available in each class of plant disease in the train set was quite balance as shown in Figure 3.

FIGURE 2. Sample images of plant disease

FIGURE 3. Number of train and test plant disease images

K-Fold cross validation was used in this model to split dataset. In 10-Fold cross validation, the data was divided into 10 subsets and was split randomly into 90-10, in which 10 partitions of data of same size was created randomly. 9 of them was used for training and 1 for testing at 10 instances of learning. During testing, every partition was used only once. To overcome the challenges of GPU memory boundaries and still use larger batch sizes which is 64 in this work, each of the images were resized to 48 X 48 and segmented for preprocessing. Augmentation process was applied to increase the dataset to reduce overfitting and to balance the distribution of the images. With the equal distribution of images in each class, it was possible to use all the data instead of choosing data randomly during training. The training accuracy will therefore be increased. Thus, random yet realistic transformations such as random horizontal flipping was applied to the training images to artificially introduce sample diversity. While slowing down overfitting, the model will also be exposed to different aspects of the training data. It was important to develop models that take raw data as

input, instead of models that take already preprocessed data. If the model expects preprocessed data, when the model is exported to be used in a web application or mobile application, the exact same preprocessing pipeline will need to be implemented. Therefore, it was necessary to do least possible amount of preprocessing before inputting the images into the model.

The preprocessed image was taken and converted into reduced variables. Figure 4 showed the architecture of CNN model used in this work. The top layer was trained and fine-tuning of the entire model was done.

FIGURE 4. Block diagram of CNN model architecture

This CNN model has input, hidden, and output layers. The hidden layers in CNN consist of

convolutional layers, pooling layers and dense layers. The first five layers in the model were Conv2D layers. These 2D convolutional layers dealt with input images. There were 64 filters in the first layer, 128 filters in the second layer, 256 filters in the third layer, 512 filters in the fourth and fifth layer. Every layer of filters were there to capture patterns. The first layer of filters captured patterns like dots, edges, corners and more. The patterns became bigger as those patterns were combined by the subsequent layers. For example, edges were combined to make circles, squares and more. As the layers increased, the patterns will get more complex. Therefore, the filter size in subsequent layers was increased to capture as many combinations as possible. The amount of pixels added to an image when it was being processed by the kernel of a CNN is the same. The convolutional layer was then passed to Max pooling to help extract low-level features like edges, points and more for better accuracy. In this pooling operation, the maximum element was chosen from the region of the feature map covered by the filter. After max-pooling layer, feature map which contained the best features of the previous feature map was the output. Each convolutional layers were added with the ReLU activation function (Rectified Linear Unit) because CNN with ReLUs trained much more quickly and reliably, thus models can learn faster and perform better. The images were passed through the layers more than once for better feature extraction.

TABLE 1. Parameters used to train CNN model

Parameters	Value
Training epoch	25
Batch size	64
Dropout	0.25
Learning rate	0.005

Based on Table 1, the training epoch was set to be 25 to train the model. The entire train dataset will pass the algorithm 25 times. More epochs increased the accuracy and decreased the loss. Thus, the plant disease classification model can predict plant disease more accurately. The model was only run once. These unique features were then sent for further processes. In this model, batch normalization layers were used to track the mean and variance of the inputs. Batch size was set to be 64. Big batch size can speed up the training and has even better generalized performances. The required GPU memory will increase when the batch size increases. A dropout layer was added before the classification layer for regularization to prevent a model from overfitting. On passing a dropout of 0.25, 25% of the nodes were dropped out randomly

from the neural network. During training, each update to a layer during training has a different “view” of the configured layer. With dropout, the accuracy will slowly increase and loss will slowly decrease. The model was compiled by using three parameters such as loss, optimizer and metrics. ‘Categorical cross entropy’ was used as the loss function. The lower score indicates that the model is performing better. Adam Optimizer with 0.05 learning rate was chosen because it was more efficient and used less time to train the neural network. Metric was used to evaluate the accuracy of the model.

Classification was a fully connected classifiers which were formed using various learnings done by the model. Three dense layers were used in this CNN model to detect and classify

the features. In dense layer, all outputs from the previous layer are fed to all its neurons so that the layer will be fully connected. The activation used was the ‘Softmax’ which gave a probability for each predicted class. The added classes will be added up to 1. The prediction was based on the class with highest probability. Images were flattened to convert the pooled images into single dimension vectors. The images were easier to be classified when the images were converted to the vectors. Certain classes had certain numerical values. Classification took place between two numerical arrays. Based on the dataset, if the numerical arrays matched, then the healthy or diseased leaf was classified. The model will detect and classify by showing the name of the plant disease and the confidence of the plant disease. The CNN model is saved and is deployed with web application and desktop application.

System integration and model deployment

Camera was used to capture leaf images. The leaf images were being uploaded to Google drive. Besides that, Pixy2 camera was connected to the PC to capture leaf images on the computer screen because we do not have real leaves. Then, the images were processed by model via web application and desktop application. Web application was developed by using HTML and CSS in Pycharm Community while desktop application was developed by using Tkinter. Since the images were taken from different camera, thus the images obtained have different qualities. The images were preprocessed to improve the image quality so that the accuracy of the system will not be affected. The developed desktop and web application is shown in Figure 5 and 6.

FIGURE 5. Desktop application

FIGURE 6. Web application

Evaluation metrics

To determine the performance of the trained CNN model, classification report and confusion matrix was shown. The training accuracy, test accuracy, training loss and test loss were shown. The graph of training accuracy and test accuracy versus epoch was plotted. The graph of training loss and test loss versus epoch was also plotted. This is to guide the fine-tuning process. Multi Class Log Loss evaluation was chosen to plot the two graphs.

$$L = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_i^N \sum_j^M y_{ij} * \ln(p_{ij}), \text{ where}$$

- N is the number of classes in the test data.
- M is the number of class labels which is 15 in this work.
- y_{ij} shows if the i -th object in the test data belongs to the j -th label which is given by a Boolean value.
- p_{ij} is the probability that the i -th object belongs to the j -th label.
- \ln is the natural logarithmic function.

A classification report and confusion matrix were used to evaluate its sensitivity and specificity. To predict the metrics of a classification report, the precision, recall and F1-score of the model were used.

Precision is the measure of accuracy in a classifier.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP}$$

Recall is the number of positive sample images that are classified correctly.

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FN}}$$

In the F1-score, the best score is 1.0 and the worst is 0.0. It is a weighted harmonic mean of recall and precision. The weighted average of F1 is used to compare classifier models. Since F1-score takes both false positives and false negatives into their computation, it is lower but more useful than accuracy measures.

$$\text{F1-score} = \frac{2 * (\text{Recall} * \text{Precision})}{\text{Recall} + \text{Precision}}$$

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The training accuracy and test accuracy were very high, which is 97.2%, while the training loss was 8.5% and test loss was 11.9%. Overfitting has good performance in training data and poor generalization to test data, while under fitting has poor performance on training data and poor generalization to test data. It was seen that the model did not experience overfitting and under fitting because the performance of the training data and the test data were good. The classification report showed the

summary of prediction results on a classification problem and the number of test images in each class. The important predictive analytics such as precision, recall, accuracy, F1-score and support values were shown in Table 2 for 15 different categorical classes. The model performs the worst when 0 and the model performs the best when 1. F1-score is used for evaluation when both precision and recall are combined. F1-score takes both false positives and false negatives into account. F1-score is more useful than precision here. This is due to the fact that false negatives are a concern. For example, the leaf actually has tomato late blight but the model classified it as tomato healthy. This is false negative. It is very important to classify the healthy and unhealthy plant disease correctly so that the plant disease can be cured efficiently. Therefore, the model performs better when F1-score is higher. Precision states whether the model is suitable to detect and classify plant disease, while calculating recall shows its weakness. To detect and classify plant disease accurately, false negatives should be avoided because they will cause bad consequences. Therefore, recall is a better measure than precision. This shows that the model can perform well with 0.97 for both average accuracy and weighted class accuracy.

TABLE 2. Classification report

	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
Pepper bell bacterial spot	1.00	0.94	0.97	80
Pepper bell healthy	0.97	0.93	0.95	76
Potato early blight	1.00	0.97	0.99	73
Potato late blight	0.95	1.00	0.98	81
Potato healthy	0.96	0.88	0.92	25
Tomato bacterial spot	1.00	0.98	0.99	110
Tomato early blight	0.96	0.90	0.93	81
Tomato late blight	1.00	0.98	0.99	93
Tomato leaf mold	1.00	0.99	0.99	73
Tomato septoria leaf spot	0.92	1.00	0.96	89
Tomato spider mites	0.94	1.00	0.97	73
Tomato target spot	0.90	0.95	0.92	97
Tomato yellow leaf curl virus	0.99	1.00	1.00	141
Tomato mosaic virus	1.00	0.98	0.99	65
Tomato healthy	1.00	1.00	1.00	97
Accuracy			0.97	1254
Macro average	0.97	0.97	0.97	1254
Weighted average	0.97	0.97	0.97	1254

A confusion matrix was plotted as in Figure 7 to analyze the misclassification between 15 different categorical plant disease classes. Each row of matrix represents 15 different predicted categorical classes while each column of matrix represents the original categorical class of plant disease. Confusion matrix in this work showed the overall classification accuracy, true positive and false rate and error rate of classification for 15 different original categorical classes. It also showed predicted plant diseases which were not classified correctly and the original plant diseases that they were mismatched with. Based on the confusion matrix, the diagonals showed that all the plant disease classes had been classified correctly, the performance of the CNN model is quite good and can extract the features well for plant disease classification.

Predicted Class \ True Class	Healthy	Tomato_early_blight	Tomato_late_blight	Tomato_spider_mites	Tomato_spider_mites_Two_spotted_spider_mite	Tomato_spider_mites_One_spotted_spider_mite	Tomato_spider_mites_Three_spotted_spider_mite	Tomato_spider_mites_Four_spotted_spider_mite	Tomato_spider_mites_Five_spotted_spider_mite	Tomato_spider_mites_Six_spotted_spider_mite	Tomato_spider_mites_Seven_spotted_spider_mite	Tomato_spider_mites_Eight_spotted_spider_mite	Tomato_spider_mites_Nine_spotted_spider_mite	Tomato_spider_mites_Ten_spotted_spider_mite	Tomato_spider_mites_Eleven_spotted_spider_mite	Tomato_spider_mites_Twelve_spotted_spider_mite	Tomato_spider_mites_Thirteen_spotted_spider_mite	Tomato_spider_mites_Fourteen_spotted_spider_mite	Tomato_spider_mites_Fifteen_spotted_spider_mite
Healthy	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tomato_early_blight	0.00	0.97	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tomato_late_blight	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tomato_spider_mites	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.95	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tomato_spider_mites_Two_spotted_spider_mite	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.96	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tomato_spider_mites_One_spotted_spider_mite	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tomato_spider_mites_Three_spotted_spider_mite	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.96	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tomato_spider_mites_Four_spotted_spider_mite	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tomato_spider_mites_Five_spotted_spider_mite	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.92	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tomato_spider_mites_Six_spotted_spider_mite	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.94	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tomato_spider_mites_Seven_spotted_spider_mite	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.04	0.90	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tomato_spider_mites_Eight_spotted_spider_mite	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.98	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tomato_spider_mites_Nine_spotted_spider_mite	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tomato_spider_mites_Ten_spotted_spider_mite	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tomato_spider_mites_Eleven_spotted_spider_mite	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tomato_spider_mites_Twelve_spotted_spider_mite	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00
Tomato_spider_mites_Thirteen_spotted_spider_mite	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00
Tomato_spider_mites_Fourteen_spotted_spider_mite	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00
Tomato_spider_mites_Fifteen_spotted_spider_mite	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

FIGURE 7. Confusion Matrix

The graph of training accuracy with respect to the epoch is plotted as in Figure 8 while the graph of training loss with respect to the epoch is also plotted as in Figure 9. The training accuracy and training accuracy have a good fit. The test accuracy was 97.2% while the test loss was 11.9%.

FIGURE 8. Model accuracy

FIGURE 9. Model loss

Figure 10-12 shows results of the correctly classified predicted class from the test image dataset which are returned with the probability of the predicted class.

FIGURE 10. Classification of healthy pepper bell leaf

FIGURE 11. Classification of early blight tomato leaf

FIGURE 12. Classification of two spotted spider mite leaf

System Integration and model deployment

The leaf images are captured by using real camera and process by model via apps to form a real-time inference vision system. The developed model has been implemented in two applications, namely desktop application which was developed by using Tkinter on python (Figure 13) with high classification accuracy (Figure 14). and web application which was developed by using HTML and CSS (Figure 15) with high classification accuracy (Figure 16). It takes less than 1 second to detect and classify plant disease in web and desktop applications.

FIGURE 13. Desktop application load image

FIGURE 14. Desktop app classification

FIGURE 15. Web application load image

FIGURE 16. Web application classification

In Figure 17, pixy2 camera was used to integrate with web or desktop applications to form a real-time inference vision system for plant disease detection and classification. In this work, the images on computer screen that displays leave obtained from internet are captured by using the camera, which leads to poor quality images due to changes in lighting and exposure. Accuracy can be affected.

FIGURE 17. Real time inference vision system for plant disease detection and classification with CNN model.

CONCLUSION

In this work, the trained CNN model shows an accuracy of 97.2% and average F1 score of 97%. In conclusion, the trained CNN model can detect and classify plant disease accurately. The trained CNN model is deployed on web application and desktop application by connecting with camera to form a real-time inference vision system. It is able to produce a useful information for farmers to apply pesticide more effectively to cure plant disease. Thus, agricultural sector can be benefited. The accuracy of the model is seek to be improved in the future.

GPU has memory issue, therefore cannot do higher level deep processing. More power GPU with more memory is needed to realize deep CNN to extract more features of plant diseases. It is also suggested to capture the real leaf images with the camera to ensure higher accuracy in the future when the Covid-19 situation gets better. Besides that, due to the situation now, VNC Viewer is used to access the GPU. In the future, when GPU lab can be entered, the CNN model that is trained can be

deployed with Pixy2 camera which is connected to the GPU to show the real-time inference vision system. The name of the plant disease will be shown directly on the AI camera when the leaf appeared on the AI camera. Since the system is trained with only 3 classes and 15 types of plant diseases, the system is proposed to be trained with many other plants and diseases to further increase the scope of the system. Extraction of many more features of the plants can be done by adding many more images of other plants to improve the accuracy of the system. By capturing many different types of plant images to add to the dataset, this dataset can be further used to build better models. Improvement of accuracy by using better algorithms in the future is proposed. An efficient bulk or spot spraying system by using the plant disease classification system is also proposed to be done in the future.

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